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Research Article

ANGER ASSESSMENT AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS¹Amina Javaid Malik, ²Sana Fatima, ³Aneeqa Riaz¹DHQ Teaching Hospital Sargodha, ²Nawaz Sharif Medical College Gujrat, ³Children hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the prevalence of anger among medical students.**Material and Methods:** A total of 115 students were included in this study. A predefined questionnaire was served. Data collected was analyzed with SPSS 23.0.**Results:** The mean age of the students was 24.05 ± 2.56 years. Regarding the frequency of anger, it was highest in final year students (93%), 86% in the fourth year, 71% in the third year, 52% in the second year and 45% in first-year students.**Conclusion:** Most of the medical students suffer from anger throughout their academic career. It can lead to physical and mental health problems leading to poor performance in studies.**Keywords:** Anger, medical education, distress, emotional behavior.**Corresponding author:****Amina Javaid Malik,**
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INTRODUCTION:

The emotional state of an individual involving annoyance, irritations, and unhappiness is considered as anger. It can vary in intensity from mild to intense feelings. Anger can lead to certain complications in a person such as cardiovascular diseases and certain musculoskeletal issues. There are certain triggers that can lead to anger. These triggers include memories of traumatic events, worrying about personal issues, getting no appreciation for one's efforts and losing patience. These feelings may be temporary or permanent in some cases [1,2].

In the medical institutes, the environment is always stressful due to tough education, dedicated ward routines, and hectic emergencies. The frequency of anger is always higher in medical institutes and hospitals etc. In hospitals, this can be due to depraved behavior of patient attendants, non-availability of basic facilities, the overburden of patients, lesser resources and lack of sleep. It will ultimately cause poor efficiency of health professionals and students leading to the collapsed health system [2-4].

Numerous studies have been conducted on the assessment of anger among health professionals and medical students⁵⁻⁷. The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence of anger in medical students in different classes. This study will help in analyzing the factors leading to certain levels of anger and will enable us in formulating strategies to minimize these

triggering factors hence leading to more productive health professionals.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study included one hundred and fifteen students from different classes. A predefined questionnaire was distributed after taking informed consent. Different questions regarding anger and triggering factors was asked. Confidentiality of the participant was ensured. The data collected was analyzed in SPSS Ver. 23.0. The qualitative variables were expressed as numbers and percentages, quantitative variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

Out of one hundred and fifteen students, ninety-three students returned the questionnaire. The response rate was 80.86%. The mean age of the students was 24.05 ± 2.56 years, minimum age noticed was 21 years and maximum age noticed was 27 years. There were 23 students (24.73%) from final year, 21 (22.58%) from the fourth year, 15 (16.13%) from the third year, 14 (15.05%) from the second year and 20 (21.51%) from the first year.

Regarding the frequency of anger, it was highest in final year students (93%), 86% in the fourth year, 71% in the third year, 52% in the second year and 45% in first-year students. Different aspects of their anger are expressed in the table.

Class	Impaired physical Health (%)	Effect on appetite (%)	Poor Decision Power (%)	Shouting (%)	Relationship issues (%)	Easy irritation (%)
1 st year	23	12	67	9	19	87
2 nd year	32	8	34	55	41	12
3 rd year	45	21	23	59	87	43
4 th year	61	32	19	42	75	23
Final year	55	42	8	21	45	7

Reasons of the anger were tough examinations (67%), irregular ward routines (45%), hostel life (23%), bad relations with the opposite gender (21%), the behavior of seniors (14%) and poor methodology (9%).

DISCUSSION:

In our study, a higher frequency of medical students was suffering from anger especially students from the final year (93%). Students studying in the final year have a tough routine i.e. they need to attend the lectures, join ward round and perform hospital duties. Their meal timings, rest time and recreations remain irregular throughout. Further, the behavior of seniors in wards or hospitals aggravates it sometimes.

Studies already conducted in Pakistan show a higher number of depression cases among medical students. The studies by Inam et al., Jadoon et al., and Bayram et al., reported similar findings in their studies³⁻⁵. Some reasons for anger and depression in their studies include assignments, dedicated and demanding studies, family pressures, hostel life and fear of future.

Dahlin and Saipanich in their studies stated that this anger and stress imposes certain negative effects on students^{6,7} i.e. they become more prone to physical and mental health issues. In our study, certain effects of included irritation on minor issues, impaired appetite,

compromised decision power, shouting and bad relationships with other students.

This study reveals interesting factors that a medical student had to face throughout their academic career. These factors should be addressed by institutional administration and relevant policies must be formulated.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the medical students suffer from anger throughout their academic career. It can lead to physical and mental health problems leading to poor performance in studies.

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